

CASE REPORT

Orthodontic treatment of pseudo-Class III malocclusion: A case report

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to present the treatment of a 26-year-old patient with Class III malocclusion with anterior crossbite using non-surgical interventions and how it improved the patient's esthetic, functional, and oral health. A lower bite plane was constructed and installed, and orthodontic treatment was done to the patient's case of malocclusion. Upper brackets were first installed in the interim to allow the upper teeth to expand before placing lower brackets on the lower teeth. After 3-6 months of observation, the removable appliance (bite plane) and fixed appliance installed on the upper teeth were successful in achieving the desired bite. On the other hand, the installation of the lower brackets retracted the lower teeth. Class III malocclusion was successfully treated and established a normal overbite with non-surgical orthodontic therapy, including the use of removable and fixed appliances.

Keywords Class III malocclusion, crossbite, orthodontics, prognathism

1 | Introduction

Class III malocclusion is defined by prognathic mandible or underdevelopment of maxilla¹ which in most cases is seen with a concave profile. According to Angle, in a Class III molar relationship, the lower first molar is mesially positioned relative to the upper first molar.² In the systematic review of Daniel et al.³, indicated Angle class III malocclusion occurrence varies substantially within

many ethnicities and geographical places, showing that the prevalence is higher among Asians and less among Caucasians, Latin Americans, and African populations. The etiological factors that may lead the patient to develop Class III malocclusion include genetics, environmental factors such as mouth breathing and postural habits, and occlusal prematurities wherein the mandible is positioned forward.¹ Ellis and McNamara⁴ conducted a study to

Figure 1. (A) Intraoral photographs and (B) diagnostic casts

determine the skeletal and dental connections of adults who have Class III malocclusion and found that 65–67% of all class III malocclusions were characterized by maxillary deficiency. Therefore, most treatment approaches rely on maxillary protraction. Treatment options for Skeletal Class III malocclusion include growth modification, orthodontic camouflage,

and orthognathic surgery.² Orthodontic camouflage is a viable alternative for the treatment of mild-to-moderate skeletal discrepancies of the maxillary structures where it disguises the skeletal problem.⁵ Nonsurgical management of Class III conditions appears to be challenging in our field. However, correct diagnosis and early

management for severe Class III malocclusion in late adolescence may be fundamental in lowering the severity of the problem.

This case report presents the use of a nonsurgical treatment approach through orthodontic camouflage which includes removable and fixed orthodontic appliances to correct the anterior crossbite and

reduce the mandibular shift with maxillary protraction and mandibular retraction. The treatment aims to achieve a pleasant profile with a harmonious relationship between the teeth and jaws and achieve a normal overbite.

Figure 2. (A) Panoramic radiograph, (B) cephalometric radiograph, and (C) cephalometric analysis

2| Case presentation section

2.1. Chief complaint

A 26-year-old male was self-conscious of his appearance and protrusive lower lips. His greatest concern was the appearance of his anterior teeth and was having trouble with eating and biting.

2.2. Medical History

There were no significant medical findings in the patient's history.

2.3. Dental History

The patient's dental history included remarkably good oral hygiene with a previous history of regular and routine dental care.

2.4. Diagnosis

On the general examination, the patient exhibited a concave profile with a prognathic chin. The intraoral examination revealed that the patient has a Class III molar relationship on the left side whereas the right side exhibited a Class I molar relationship with a forward functional mandibular shift causing the incisors to occlude in an anterior crossbite. He was diagnosed with Class III malocclusion with an anterior crossbite (Figure 1A). The upper arch presented mild crowding. From a dental perspective,

the patient presented Angle Class III malocclusion; in which the mesial slope of the upper canine lies behind the distal slope of the lower canine, and the mesiobuccal cusp of the permanent maxillary first molar lies behind the mesiobuccal groove of the permanent mandibular first molar (Figure 1B).

Panoramic radiograph (Figure 2A) showed that all of the teeth had healthy root development, however, the upper and lower anterior teeth were supraerupted. No evidence of lesions, cysts, and fractures. The mandibular left third molar was impacted while the right one has been previously extracted. Cephalometric radiograph and analysis (Figure 2B-C, Table 1) revealed that the patient has a class III jaw relationship based on the retrognathic maxilla, prognathic mandible, and a hypodivergent growth pattern.

Table 1. Cephalometric analysis measurements

Area of Study	Measurement	Normal Value	Value	Interpretation
Cranial Base	Ba-S-N	130°	119	Anteriorly inclined clivus
Maxillary to cranial base	SNA	82°	78.5°	Retrognathic maxilla
	N-A-Fh	90°	82°	Retrognathic maxilla
Mandible to cranial base	SNB	80°	87°	Prognathic mandible
	NPog-Fh	88°	96°	Prognathic mandible
Maxillo-mandibular relationship	ANB	2°	-8°	Sk class III
	Wits	2mm	-2mm	Sk class III
Vertical Height	SN-MPA	32°	25°	Hypodivergent
	FMA	25°	19°	Hypodivergent
Maxillary-Mandibular Incisor Position	UI-SN	104°	124°	Proclined upper incisors
	UI-Na (mm)	4mm	7mm	Proclined upper incisors
	IMPA	90°	87°	Reclined lower incisors
	LI-NB (mm)	4mm	1mm	Reclined lower incisors
	LI-NB	25°	15°	Reclined lower incisors
	LI-APog	2mm	-1mm	Reclined lower incisors
Soft Tissue	E-Line - Lower lip	-2mm	2mm	Protruded lower lip

2.5. Prognosis

Orthodontic treatment for skeletal Class III malocclusion has a good prognosis. The prognosis of the case was favorable since the patient presented a small gonial angle and hypodivergent growth pattern and thus was able to perform the treatment with orthodontic camouflage. However, if the patient is not treated and negligent, Class III malocclusion could worsen. Early treatment is advised for this to achieve a healthy skeletal relationship.

2.6 Treatment

Figure 3. (A) Lower bite plane installed (B) Upper brackets installed on the maxillary teeth (C) Presence of open bite

Before any orthodontic procedure, tooth #38 was extracted to prevent further movement and crowding. A non-surgical approach was initiated for the treatment of the patient as opposed to orthodontic surgery. Orthodontic camouflage treatment was decided as the treatment option which includes increasing the vertical dimension, maxillary arch advancement, and mandibular arch retraction. The initial treatment given was the installation of the removable

acrylic appliance (posterior bite plane) on the mandibular teeth to relieve the occlusion (Figure 3-A). The bite plane was installed in the posterior teeth to raise the patient's bite and allow the labial movement of the maxillary incisors. After raising the patient's bite, a fixed appliance (Optimum bracket 0.22mm) with 0.12 NiTi archwire was placed first on the maxillary teeth (Figure 3-B) followed by 0.14 and 0.16 NiTi archwire to achieve protraction and proclination of the maxillary arch resulting in the increased arch circumference and length and permitted crossbite correction. The

anterior crossbite was corrected within 4 months and resulted in an open bite (Figure 3-C).

The treatment of the mandibular teeth began three months after the installation of the fixed appliance on the maxillary teeth with the use of 0.12 NiTi archwire. This procedure allowed the retraction of the mandibular arch. After 4 months, after the installation of the mandibular fixed appliance, the arch wire of the maxillary teeth was changed into

0.16x0.16ss archwire and was then followed on the mandibular teeth with 0.16x22ss archwire to stabilize the dental arches. The open bite was corrected and established a positive overbite within 10 months (Figure 4). The patient was satisfied with the results of the fixed and removable orthodontic treatment. The patient's crossbite was corrected and the smile aesthetic was improved.

3 | Discussion

Figure 4. Positive overbite

The patient's chief complaint was the unaesthetic appearance of his teeth exhibiting a class III malocclusion with an anterior crossbite. Treatment alternatives for a full-grown skeletal class III patient include orthognathic surgery and orthodontic camouflage.⁶ Orthognathic surgery is recommended for adult patients with large dentoskeletal discrepancies and is ideal for achieving a normal occlusion and esthetic profile. Orthodontic camouflage (dentoalveolar compensation) is recommended for milder discrepancies.⁷ In this case, the patient refused the surgical

intervention and preferred the camouflage treatment.

A successful Class III camouflage can be foreseen through the common cephalometric predictors for the evaluation of the maxillary and mandibular which include: ANB ($< -2^\circ$ to -3°), Wits appraisal (-2 to -6 mm for nonsurgical treatment, -6 to -9 mm for a compromised result) and a maxillomandibular differential and gonial angle within normal range. The "Wits" appraisal is the most important

factor in deciding on camouflage treatment from the surgical option.¹ In the case, presented a "Wits" appraisal of -2 mm and a skeletal severity level of ANB = -8° establishing a skeletal class III malocclusion which directed the orthodontic camouflage treatment in addition to the patient's decision.

The treatment involved correcting the anterior crossbite with the use of removable and fixed appliances through dentoalveolar compensation by labial proclination of upper incisors and lingual retroclination of lower incisors. Alami et al. have suggested that a combination of both fixed and

removable appliances are indicated in treating anterior crossbite. Both appliances offer heavy intermittent forces or light-continuous forces that are ideal for tooth movement.⁸ In the case, the crossbite caused a minimal space for bracket adhesion therefore, the posterior bite plane was first installed to disocclude the maxillary and mandibular teeth⁹ and raise the patient's bite. It was then followed by the placement of fixed appliances for maxillary labial flaring and mandibular retraction. A temporary open bite occurred during the treatment. According to Proffit et al.², in adults where growth is largely completed, bite opening probably will be required to give enough space for the lingually displaced maxillary incisor before attempting to move it facially into arch form. At the end of the case, crossbite correction was achieved, and established a normal overbite. Establishing a good overbite relationship is the key to maintain the crossbite correction.²

4 | Conclusions

This case report presented a non-traditional treatment modality to treat deep anterior crossbite in an adult class III malocclusion complicated by supraerupted upper and lower incisors. The treatment of deep anterior crossbite was technically challenging due to the difficulty of placing the fixed appliance, therefore it must be

accompanied by a bite plane. The Class III malocclusion with anterior crossbite was successfully treated through orthodontic camouflage, a non-surgical therapy. The use of a fixed appliance with a removable posterior bite plane effectively tipped maxillary incisors labially and mandibular incisors lingually to correct the patient's anterior crossbite establishing a normal overbite.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank Dr. Ruffa Quirante for her willingness in sharing her knowledge and expertise in this case report and the faculty members of the Southwestern University PHINMA School of Dentistry for their support in this study.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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